

● The professional in the field ensures that products of animal origin are in compliance with quality standards, are safe for human consumption, and meet sanitary regulations, explains the specialist Pamela Valquerizo

The veterinarian's performance is vital in the quality of items of animal origin

Health

From the Editorial Staff
contato@jornaldezminutos.com.br

Specialist in food quality control, veterinarian Pamela Valquerizo highlights the role of the veterinary doctor in ensuring the quality of products of animal origin.

What is the relationship between food and medicine throughout history, and how have they been interconnected?

The relationship between food and medicine dates back to ancient civilizations, where there were already concerns about the quality and proper consumption of food. Based on empirical knowledge, they perceived the cause-and-effect relationship between certain foods and well-being or illness.

Can we cite specific examples of this concern with food quality in the past?

In India, for example, as early as 300 B.C., a law was enacted that prohibited the adulteration of cereals, medicines, and perfumes. The ancient Egyptians also demonstrated attention to food, although in a more limited way. Bread and beer were their main foods, but the lack of hygiene and the presence of sand in the desert, which contaminated the bread, caused health problems, such as the wear of teeth

In a broader scenario, how have these changes impacted society?

The changes in food production and hygiene measures have had a significant impact on public health.

Veterinarian Pamela Valquerizo provides an overview of the performance of these professionals in public health

In the past, epidemics such as malaria, leprosy, and tuberculosis were frequent, reducing the life expectancy of the population. However, with the increase in knowledge about safe food practices and the implementation of hygiene measures, such as animal inspection and the improvement of sanitary conditions, public health began to strengthen, and life expectancy gradually increased.

Could you give us some reflections on the importance of this history for the present?

These lessons from the past remind us that food safety and public health are ongoing issues that require attention and effective regulations to protect the population. We must value the knowledge acquired over the centuries and apply it in our modern society, ensuring a healthy life for all.

What were the significant changes in the way food was produced and consumed?

An important turning point was the emergence of prepared foods, whether industrialized or manipulated. With large-scale production, problems with foodborne diseases began to arise due to inadequate preservation. This led to the implementation of laws and regulations in subsequent centuries, such as the 'Bread Assize' in England, which prohibited the addition of peas and beans to bread dough.

And what about hygiene and public health, when did these issues start to receive more attention?

Only in the 13th century did the first standards for meat inspection and slaughterhouses appear in Europe. At the same time, other laws were enacted to protect the consumer, such

as the prohibition of trading sick animals. It is worth noting that this historical period was marked by great epidemics and calamities.

What is the role of the veterinary doctor in the quality of animal-origin products?

The veterinary doctor plays an essential role in ensuring the quality and safety of animal-origin products. Their role ranges from the supervision and inspection of establishments and production processes to the prevention of diseases and the promotion of animal welfare. It is their responsibility to ensure that animal-origin products are in compliance with quality standards, are safe for human consumption, and meet sanitary regulations.

And what are the main activities performed by veterinary doctors?

They monitor and inspect the production facilities. They assess the health of the animals, ensure that they are being raised and fed properly, carry out diagnostic tests for diseases, implement sanitary control measures, and ensure the quality of the final products. These professionals play a fundamental role in educating the producers.

How does the care for the well-being of animals contribute to the quality of animal-origin products?

Animals raised in proper conditions, with balanced nutrition, access to clean water, and suitable spaces, tend to have a lower incidence of diseases. In addition, proper handling and reduction of stress in animals during slaughter and production also influence the quality of meat, milk, eggs, and other products.

What are the challenges faced by veterinarians in this area?

One of the main challenges is the prevention and control of diseases in animals, which can affect human health and food production. In addition, it is important to deal with complex sanitary regulations, stay up-to-date on the best practices and available technologies, and promote awareness about the importance of the quality of products of animal origin.